

Electronic monitoring of small arthropods in closed mesocosms

Detailed presentation of a practical tool

Abstract

The study of small animals in habitat containing coarse substrates of similar granularity (soil, manure, dust...) is hampered by the great difficulties in monitoring the daily activity and demographic dynamics of populations in their environment. However, this is a major issue to improve the management of wingless hematophagous vectors, to progress understanding the role of microarthropods in humus formation as well as in fundamental understanding foraging behaviors and trophic interactions in social insects. The use of experimental units such as mesocosms or experimental anthills provides information on general effects of the groups' activity, but does not allow to unravel processes. On the other hand, recently developed electronic tracking tools allow the study of animal behavior *in vitro*.

We have designed a new mixed experimental system that allows observation of both the development of invertebrate populations in environments similar to their natural environment and continuous electronic monitoring of the activity of individuals at one or more strategic points, including over several generations. The electronic tracking system can be replicated, so as to monitor several units and/or several points per unit at the same time.

Key words: experimental manipulations, closed mesocosms, nanocomputer, electronic tracking, population dynamics, mite, vector, central place forager

1 Motivations and constraints of the method

The study of group behavior and population dynamics of small animals growing in habitats containing coarse substrates such as soil and manure is inherently challenging. Many mites and insects (e.g. ants, termites...) spend their lives in substrates consisting of multitudes of irregular particles whose granularity is in part similar to their own size. This typically keeps them out of reach of extensive observations and is an impediment to the understanding of certain ecological processes involving their interactions [1]. Overcoming this

obstacle is a major challenge not only for progress on operational questions such as the management of pests such as certain hematophagous vectors that thrive in livestock or the contribution of microarthropods to soil quality for crops, but also on fundamental questions concerning group behavior and trophic interactions (e.g., study of key foragers such as ants).

Interactions between invertebrate populations or communities and their substrate have been mostly investigated by comparing initial and final population sizes or intermittent direct behavioral observation in closed experimental units mimicking portions of ecosystems (usually called mesocosms or microcosms; e.g. [2]), which hinders access to the continuous dynamics of animal activity. On the other hand, recently, electronic tracking tools involving increasingly affordable computer systems are being developed for the *in-vitro* studies on insect behavior, e.g. [3]. Combining the two broad types of methods has the potential to generate valuable tools, but this requires substantial adaptations.

We decided to take advantage of a type of closed mesocosm that we recently developed to cultivate poultry arthropods in near-field conditions [4,5]. *Dermanyssus gallinae* (de Geer, 1778) is strictly hematophagous mite (it needs bird blood to perform its metamorphosis and to lay eggs). It lives at a distance from the host, in various substrates and interstices in farm buildings and bird nests. This small, wingless vector is responsible for significant damage in layer farms worldwide [6]. Its aggregated and remote lifestyle from the host makes its population dynamics particularly difficult to characterize both in farms and in the laboratory. Experiments on several generations of mites (i.e. several weeks/months) involving chickens have been conducted in cages [7] and more recently in mite-proof mesocosms [4,5]. In the first studies (in cages), the dynamics of population growth were evaluated by counting mites in passive traps. To avoid this type of invasive intervention and to provide accurate counts, Zriki et al. [4,5] used the final count and therefore did not assess population growth during the experiment.

In order to refine our understanding of the temporal dynamics of *D. gallinae* populations, we have developed a multi-target tracking system adapted to *in-situ* counting of arthropods. The measurement of foraging activity over several generations was intended to complete the characterization of the growth of populations of *D. gallinae*. More generally, our tracking tool can be used for a variety of other studies involving diverse invertebrates (other hematophagous arthropods, other mites, ants...), either in closed mesocosms or in other contexts. As long as a strategic area can be identified on which the counting can be focused, the activity of various invertebrates can be recorded over relatively long periods. Here we present in detail the 'multi-target electronic tracking' part of a

study integrating this system in closed mesocosms described in an article currently under revision.

2 Design of the experimental system

In order to capture the dynamics of population activity across multiple generations in small invertebrates that dwell in coarse substrates, we considered the following five conditions:

- (1) availability of at least one resource source,
- (2) ‘invertebrate-proof’ system,
- (3) Replication of the system (must allow to conduct experiments with at least ten true replicates),
- (4) possibility to recover all invertebrates at the end of the experiment,
- (5) non-destructive quantification of the population over time.

Our closed mesocosms were previously designed to meet the first four conditions for *D. gallinae* [4,5]: large enough to house a 1-7-week-old chick (1), ventilated but mite-proof (2), small enough to keep several dozens in operation in an air-conditioned room (3) and that the interior can be completely rinsed to recover the invertebrates at the end of the experiment (4). To meet the fifth condition (5), we developed an optical tracking system recording the foraging activity of mites by systematically counting the mites going to (or leaving) the support on which a bird host is maintained.

For such a purpose, we have modified 10 mesocosms to force mites to pass through a single optical tracking zone to obtain their blood meal and positioned a nano-computer controlled camera on this specific zone in each mesocosm. Each mesocosm is equipped with its own camera and nano-computer, which records the passage of the mites and their direction.

The tracking device (Fig. Z1A) consisted of an electronic assembly involving an ARM processor single board nanocomputer (Raspberry pi 3 model B, Cambridge, UK), a 8 megapixel infrared camera equipped with an on-board lens (Pi NoIR Camera v2) and a 940 nm infrared LED strip (Solarex, Dessau-Roßlau, Germany). All detailed technical, mechanical and computer information is available on the MiteThru github: <https://github.com/LR69/MiteThru/>). The camera was placed behind the Plexiglas disc, in a central position (Fig. 1B of the present article and Fig. Z1). The bar giving the sole access to the perch where the chick rests was fitted in the center of the Plexiglas disc, so that mites must cross the Plexiglas disc from the perimeter to the center to reach the chick. The

electronic assembly was carried out with pieces obtained through RS Components, UK and Farnell, UK (assembly diagram and complete list of material on MiteThru github). A Python program using openCV library (<https://opencv.org/>) counted each individual mite crossing the plexiglass disc as "IN" (towards the host) or "OUT" (the other way round) (Fig. Z1B; full program on the MiteThru github). The acquisition of monitoring data can be performed continuously or at selected times. In our study, it was carried out during complete nights, as well as during periods of two complete days (nights included). We made sure to record all periods when chicks were present in order to obtain an accurate census of mites that fed during the experiment. Each nano-computer integrated a web server that was used to monitor the experiment in each individual mesocosm and to retrieve data, in a form of a csv file, and to provide trend curves showing the evolution of the number of "IN" and "OUT" mites during the entire recording periods. All nano-computers of the different mesocosms in operation during the experiment (replicates) were connected to a wifi access point, that allowed interconnection of all nano-computers with experimenters' personal computers. It also ensured an accurate and constant time setting.

3 Validation and implementation of the system

In order to exclude the counting of possible astigmatic mites and other possible artifacts, we evaluated the size variations of the mites and set size thresholds in pixel² beyond which objects were not counted during experiments. We also took the opportunity to evaluate the usefulness of a size distinction to account for mite stage/sex (see below). For such purposes, size range of *D. gallinae* was defined by releasing successively dozens of groups of 50 live mites belonging to a single life stage/sex group: protonymphs / deutonymphs + adult males / adult females, determined under a stereomicroscope as in Bartley et al. [8] on the Plexiglas disc. To prevent the mites from leaving the disc, it was surrounded by a circle of washing-up liquid, which forms an impenetrable barrier for them. We recorded the sizes of any individual crossing the limit, in either direction (IN and OUT).

The frequency distribution of counted mite sizes provided means, standard deviations, and ranges for the three stage-sex groups. Thresholds for excluding counts were set outside the extreme values to avoid the counting of objects other than *D. gallinae* (possible dust, light variations).

To verify that the mite count was correct, we inoculated two mesocosms with a mix of several hundred starving and alive mites of all stages and sexes. We

FIGURE Z1. Tracking device. A. View of a tracking system. B. Counting principle of the tracking program. The disc represents the area of the plexiglas disc where mites are

recorded by the tracking device. The bar giving access to the perch where the chicken is resting is fitted on the center of the disc. Three pictures are taken every second on average. The program considers on each picture a tracking zone (light grey), a reference zone (dark grey), a counting zone (green) and a border (red). “IN” and an “OUT” counters are associated with each size group (here, a single size group). When a mite enters the tracking zone, it is “seen” by the software but has no visible identifier (1). When the mite enters the reference zone, an identifier is assigned to it (2). When a tracked mite enters the outside counting zone, crosses the border and exits from the inside counting zone, the “IN” counter is incremented (3). When a tracked mite crosses in the opposite direction, the “OUT” counter is incremented. When a mite leaves the reference zone, it loses its identifier (4).

made more than 20 video captures, each lasting 15 seconds and distributed over 5 nights with a chick present and verified that automatic and visual counts were similar. Mites observed entering the reference zone were properly labeled, those crossing the boundary were all counted, and those that did not cross were not. We have observed the occasional deposit of dust on the Plexiglas disk, but this did not cause any data acquisition (no crossing movement). Similarly, slight light variations induced false mite detection but these were not counted as IN or OUT.

3.1 Setting alerts that trigger the recording of photos

In order to detect possible problems, alerts were programmed when (1) the number of mites referenced at the same time was >10 (upper triggering threshold), (2) an object exceeded the maximum threshold defined above. At each alert, the sequence of photos taken during 15 seconds was recorded and visually checked. The recordings triggered by the alerts showed in most cases a number of mites moving on the Plexiglas disk higher than the set threshold, which led to the above-mentioned counting procedure. Sometimes non-problematic artifacts mentioned above (due to slight light variation) were responsible for the alert. On only one occasion ants accidentally entered mesocosms. The three ant alerts occurred in two mesocosms the same week when a local ant invasion had been observed in the experimental room. We implemented ant management actions in the room (treatment with baits, application of glue, feet of the tables supporting the mesocosms in basins of soapy water,) and in the mesocosms (removal of single ants from two of them, interruption-cleaning and reset of the experiment for one of them). The new mixed system (TR mesocosms) is indeed more vulnerable to contamination than STD mesocosms because of recurrent introductions/removals of chicks, but the alert system allowed us to detect unwanted introductions and to intervene.

3.2 Classifying mites into size classes

We defined a size threshold for mites in order to count the mites in two classes corresponding respectively to adult females and other life stages/sex as follows: during the preliminary tests for the definition of size thresholds (see above), the frequency distribution of sizes obtained by groups of life stages allowed us to detect an interesting bimodality, despite a partial overlap, between adult females and other life stages. We used the value in the middle of the overlap area, farthest from the frequency peaks of the two groups. Consequently, the size threshold used to distinguish adult females from other life stages/sexes, was set at 200 pixels. Assignment of individuals to size groups was performed during the last four nights in the presence of hens. The data obtained included individuals classified as 'adult females' and individuals classified as 'other life stages/sex' in the category of IN individuals, and the same two groups in the category of OUT individuals. Interestingly, the median proportion of individuals assigned to the 'adult female' category relative to others by the optical system was >0.6 while it was close to 0.3 in the shelters for physically counted individuals. This suggests a much higher activity of adult females than others, but could also be due to a size assignment defect.

In order to evaluate the relevance of the threshold for *D. gallinae*, we performed similar tests as described above on 173 individuals which were all, after recording during 5 min, mounted on microscope slides in lactic acid and observed under the microscope to assign the precise sex and life stage. This allowed us to assess the variation in sizes in pixels per individual and life stage/sex. The results confirmed that the two size groups corresponded roughly to adult females and other life stages/sexes, with the sizes recorded for adult males largely overlapping those of deutonymphs (Fig. Z2 below). They also showed marked intra-individual variation, probably resulting from the wide movements of the mite while walking ($26\% \pm 15\%$ of the mean per mite; Fig. Z3). The width of the area covered by the mite's body on the Plexiglas plate oscillates widely with each step due to changes in orientation of the sagittal axis relative to the surface, exposing a variable surface to the tracker. The overlapping area was considered too large to allow an accurate discrimination of the life stages.

As a result of the threshold set, separating these two groups allowed a correct assignment in the majority of cases but the precision was insufficient to get a fine enough overview of the life stage/sex successions in *D. gallinae*. Nevertheless, counting individuals grouped by size class is quite feasible with our system and this could be interesting for arthropods with more marked size

groups. This could be judiciously applied to explore the population dynamics of two species in interaction (e.g. prey-predators). The possibility of defining size thresholds is included in this code.

4 Conclusions and perspectives

The main achievements of the new method are continuous records of mite activity that reflects the population size and for various size classes. This study establishes the proof of concept of a system comprising a closed mesocosm, an IR camera, a nanocomputer and a Python program that can be replicated dozens of times and implemented simultaneously in the same experimental room. This system may be used for studies on : (1) population dynamics: temporal evolution of population size, life history traits, population increase rate, calibrating models of population dynamics; (2) temporal dynamics of size classes recorded simultaneously (e.g. several age classes or several species of distinct sizes); (3) determinism of population growth: effect of abiotic factors (structure of the environment, temperature, HR), effect of host or food source availability and quality, effect of biotic interactions (predation, competition); (4) Chronobiology; (5) Experimental evolution.

The tracker-mesocosm combination is particularly interesting to study ectoparasites that do not live on host such as micropredators, because they have predictable paths and make regular return trips to the host. The population dynamics of many micropredators of economic or health importance is poorly known, e.g. the poultry red mite *D. gallinae* (Acari: Dermanyssidae), bedbugs *Cimex lectularius* and other *Cimex* (Insecta:

FIGURE Z2. Distribution of mean size of mites recorded at the time of crossing the "border" line per stage and sex. D = deutonymph, F = female adult, M = male adult, P = protonymph.

FIGURE Z3. Distribution of the coefficient of variation (standard deviation divided by

the mean) calculated for each mite.

Cimicidae), and triatomine bugs (Insecta: Reduviidae). Soft ticks (Acari: Argasidae) present an intermediate lifestyle between micropredator and typical ectoparasites because the larvae stay a few days on the host but blood meals by subsequent life stages are short and the rest of the time is spent in the environment of the host. There is therefore the possibility to follow nymphs and adults in this taxon too. More generally the tracker can be used to monitor any vagile arthropod, provided that one can expect the passage of individuals at a specific location so that counts reliably represent activity level and/or population size (e.g. key foragers such as ants).

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